

The Learning Process in Future Preparations: Middle-Aged and Older Adults' Experiences

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Abstract : Taiwan will become an aging society in 2018. The method to face the challenges related to the aging population has become an important topic. Purpose: This study aims to understand the future preparation of middle-age and older adults, and how they prepared themselves to face the problems of aging, and how they took actions to plan and cope with their future life. Moreover, how did they generate the process of learning action, so that they would be able to live a more active and meaningful life when they entered into their older age? Method: We conducted semi-structure interviews with 10 middle-aged and older adults who had taken actions to prepare for their future. We examined the interviewees' consciousness and learning actions in their future preparation. Preliminary Results: 1. The triggering factors of the interviewees' consciousness to prepare for the future included: family events, the desire to maintain active social lives after retirement, the continuation of the interviewees' professional careers after retirement, and the aspiration for participation in volunteer services. 2. 'Health problems' and 'economic security' were issues of the utmost concern for the interviewees' future. However, they would transform these worries to learning actions, comprising of active participation in learning, finding relevant information through learning; thus, accumulating more resources to cope with their future needs.

Keywords : middle-age and older adults, preparing for future, older adult learning

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